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The Platform for Sharing, Initiating and
Learning Citizen Science in Europe

Deliverable 3.2

**Citizen science resource gap
and opportunities analysis**

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Abstract	This report presents the outcomes of task T3.3 Resource gap analysis and opportunity identification within work package 3 Content - Framework, Quality Assurance and Curation. The specific task of T3.3, as reported here, was to identify gaps in citizen science resources on the EU-Citizen.Science platform, based on prevalent resource needs and to recommend pathways and activities to close the resource gaps.
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Definitions and Acronyms

CS	Citizen science
CSO	Civil society organisation
CSTH	Citizen Science Translation Hub
DIY	Do it yourself
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
Metadata	A description of data
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
SwafS	Science with and for Society
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The aim of the EU-Citizen.Science project is to build a sustainable platform and a mutual learning space for citizen science (CS) in Europe through an inclusive and transparent approach. This report presents the outcomes of task T3.3 Resource gap analysis and opportunity identification within work package (WP) 3 Content - Framework, Quality Assurance and Curation. The activities in WP3 aim to collect state-of-the art and high quality resources for the CS community, available via the EU-Citizen.Science platform, such as tools, guidelines and materials (TGMs) of all kinds, summarised as *citizen science resources*. The specific task of T3.3, as reported here, was to identify gaps in CS resources on the EU-Citizen.Science platform, based on prevalent resource needs and to recommend pathways on how to close the resource gaps.

I Introduction

I.1 The EU-Citizen.Science project

EU-Citizen.Science aims to build a sustainable platform and mutual learning space to mainstream citizen science as a means to address societal challenges of our time and for the future. The platform is the space where (i) initiatives, (ii) resources and (iii) outcomes that are relevant to CS are collected, curated, and made accessible to everyone, including volunteers, policy makers, media and academic institutions, among others. This ambitious agenda will be pursued through the following complementary activities:

- Coordination of CS actions and leveraging of existing resources in the presently fragmented landscape of CS in Europe;
- Engagement of quadruple helix stakeholders at all levels (local, national and European);
- Creation of a platform that will serve as a mutual learning space and a set of comprehensive training programmes, co-designed with and for different target audiences to address their needs.

EU-Citizen.Science adopts a transparent and inclusive approach in realizing the aforementioned objectives and promotes interdisciplinary, cross-border, cross-sector collaboration. Its potential is expected to give rise to social innovation and new business models by stimulating new partnerships, and to promote effective, participatory and transparent decision making at various spatial and temporal scales within Europe. By consolidating activities, integrating knowledge and outputs, and increasing capacities at the local, national and global level, EU-Citizen.Science aims to build the platform that has the potential to be the “centre” for citizen science in Europe and beyond. With 14 partners and nine third parties from 14 European countries, and a variety of stakeholders

representing networks, universities, CSOs, local authorities, natural history museums, and others, the project has the potential to achieve this goal.

1.2 WP 3: Content - Framework, Quality Assurance and Curation

WP3 of the EU-Citizen.Science project aims to develop an operational framework to identify and facilitate the collection and sharing of high-quality resources and best practices of CS. The main objectives of WP3 are to:

- Deliver criteria and a living quality roadmap that help define and identify:
 - CS resources and best practices, and
 - Quality criteria that can be applied to the aforementioned materials for selecting them in the frame of the EU-Citizen.Science online platform;
- Curate current resources that could be useful to a broad set of actors from inexperienced users to professionals, from policy makers to career scientists, which facilitate their engagement with citizen science.

WP3 consists of three essential tasks:

- Task 3.1 Criteria definition for collecting and sharing best practices in CS
- Task 3.2 Collating state of the art in CS: tools, guidelines and materials
- Task 3.3 CS resource gap analysis and opportunity identification

1.3 Purpose and scope of the resource gap analysis and identification of opportunities to close resource gaps (T3.3)

The purpose was to identify existing gaps in CS resources on the EU-Citizen.Science platform and find appropriate ways to close the gaps to support one of the main aims of the project, namely to leverage existing resources in a fragmented landscape of CS in Europe as well as to provide a one-stop shop for high-quality and much needed CS resources in Europe. To achieve this, several steps were taken as part of an iterative process (Figure 1) to answer four important questions.

- 1) An initial *resource needs analysis* was conducted, to answer the question: What kind of resources do different audiences need?
- 2) A *resource status analysis* then established the status quo of the EU-Citizen.Science platform and the kind of resources it had gathered by a certain date, answering: What kind of resources are available on the EU-Citizen.Science platform after the first few months since its launch?
- 3) The *identification of resource gaps* then aimed at answering: What are the emerging gaps, if we compare resource needs (Q1) with the available resources online (Q2)?

- 4) The *identification of opportunities* to close resource gaps was concerned with the question: How can we best close the gaps and provide the CS community with what it needs?

Figure 1: Iterative process of resource gap and opportunity analysis

This report documents in detail the methods and results of the above outlined steps. Needs for resources were identified based on a stakeholder and target audience needs survey, expert input from the consortium and the citizen science field, as well as challenges identified by the European Commission (EC). Identified needs were then mapped against existing resources on the EU-Citizen.Science platform by a certain cut-off date (July 14, about four months after the launch of the platform). Gaps were identified and documented based on (1) no available resource for an identified need, (2) quality assessment of available resources not suitable to meet identified need, (3) availability in different languages, (4) and partial suitability or applicability. Furthermore, this report outlines opportunities for the creation of resources to close the identified resource gaps on the EU-Citizen.Science platform, considering actions within the project, via outreach to other SwafS and RIA projects, as well as mobilising the wider CS community.

2 Resource needs

2.1 Gathering needs

We aimed to elicit resource needs identified by different stakeholder groups, namely CS experts and practitioners, the wider CS community, and funders and decision makers concerned with CS. To achieve this, we implemented different methods to gather data and information for further analysis:

1) an expert consultation via a participatory mapping and clustering workshop, 2) an online survey targeted at CS practitioners, the wider CS community and related networks, as well as 3) desktop research on challenges/needs identified by the EC using the SwafS funding call text.

The expert consultation was held during the EU-Citizen.Science proposal meeting in Berlin in February 2018 with 26 CS experts (see Appendix 1 for full list of participants). In a joint mapping exercise they identified resource needs and gaps on post-its and discussed them in three sub-groups before reporting back and discussing them in the plenary setting. For the purpose of this report, the post-it documentation and meeting notes were used as a basis for the needs analysis.

The online survey (see Appendix 2) was conducted in collaboration with WP5 and is described in detail in the public report: *D5.1 Report on Training Needs*. For this report, responses to online survey question 3 (“In your opinion, what kinds of new training resources are needed in Citizen Science?”) were considered to substantiate and identify all kinds of CS resource needs. Often, respondents indicated needs for a specific resource rather than needs for a specific form of training when answering this survey question (see definitions in section 3.1). Survey question 3 received 63 responses from the CS practitioner community and extended networks, including science centers, museums, science education and communication, hands-on and DIY science, etc.

The *SwafS-15-2018-2019 Exploring and supporting citizen science* call text (Appendix 3) served as the third information source for identifying CS resource needs. Funding call texts are one important means for the EC to communicate needs as perceived at EC level, through identifying challenges and posing expected impacts. These call texts help understand needs from a higher-level policy viewpoint and can give insights into where the EC puts specific emphasis and expects innovation.

2.2 Analysing needs

2.2.1 Thematic analysis

The data gathered was screened and prepared for thematic analysis (Boyatzis, 1998; Braun and Clarke, 2013), which subsequently followed a six step process. First, the raw information was examined, and original needs formulations were split into individually identifiable needs. Second, if applicable, named audiences were identified and assigned to a broader audience group. Third, the details and nuances of the individual resource needs were explored, from which specific themes emerged. These were then used to cluster the needs for further analysis (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Six step process of thematic analysis used to identify resource needs

Overall, respondents of the expert consultation and the online survey chose to address the question for resource needs, or gaps, mainly in two ways:

- 1) Specifically listing and naming needed resources, or
- 2) Offering a narrative around a specific resource need, often indicating specific audiences, providing examples or describing potential use cases.

Furthermore, a difference in specificity could be observed, ranging from generic and very broad to specific resource descriptions, e.g. “Bottom-up resources” (broad, generic) and “Guidance for handling private data (including names, e-mail addresses, location, images etc.) esp. matching the needs under GDPR” (specific).

From the raw data material, 128 individual needs were identified, most of which stemmed from the online survey with the wider CS practitioner community (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Individual needs identified per data source (% of total)

Table 1 provides examples of how individual needs from the different sources were expressed.

Table 1: Different individually identifiable needs by source

Original need formulation	Data source
"Quality assurance tool"	Expert consultation
"Toolkits for integrating CS with education"	Expert consultation
"Missing: Guide on how to manage communication + engagement in CS"	Expert consultation
"What is needed for the field, however, is a way to easily create [project-specific] resources by using plug-and-play templates and software tools generated by the community."	Online Survey
"I would mostly like practical tools over reports: action plans, checklists etc."	Online Survey
"Guidance for handling private data (including names, e-mail addresses, location, images etc.) esp. matching the needs under GDPR;"	Online Survey
"How to make CS transferable in other domains. I am [...] a researcher on social networked (language) education and fascinated by the CS achievements but it is difficult for my colleagues and me to see how we can launch CS projects in areas such as language learning and teaching, or in user engagement in creation of resources in their own languages."	Online Survey
"[Guidance on] managing large numbers of volunteers for many months or even years..."	SwafS call text
"Availability of tools, guidelines, or other materials useful to actors inexperienced in organising and supporting citizen science initiatives"	SwafS call text

Figure 4: Audiences identified in needs formulations

However, many times specific audience groups were either included in the needs formulation (e.g. funders audience: "Special info for funders of CS > what is special, what is different?"), or the intended audience became apparent based on how the need was expressed (e.g., researchers and

scientists: “How to start considering a citizen science approach to address their own research needs”). In some cases, more than one target group was mentioned as an audience in relation to a needed resource. From the explicitly and implicitly mentioned audiences, nine groups could be identified (Figure 4). These are researchers/scientists, CS practitioners, citizen scientists, citizens, teachers, activists, journalists, funders, and policy makers. There were many instances, though, where no audience was specified, nor clearly suggested.

2.3 Needs and needs themes

Two overarching distinctions emerged from the data on how people chose to describe resources. Some focused the description on a specific content topic, others focused on the type of resource.

- **Resource topic:** the resource need was described to help with a specific topic or topical area in citizen science (e.g., engagement, data quality and standards, regulations and ethics)
- **Resource type:** described specifying the kind or type of resource needed, in addition, or irrespective of its content (e.g., best practices, citizen science stories, instructables, introduction to CS, bottom-up resources, online tools etc.)

Figure 5: Audiences identified in needs formulations (some needs formulation mentioned a specific audience group, and some included more than one audience specification for the same need)

Within these two distinctions, several themes could be identified, forming the final topical and type-based needs themes (Figure 5): Best practices, Co-creation, Communication, CS stories, Data quality and standards, Empowerment, Engagement, Evaluation of CS, Event planning, Impact, Instructables, Introduction to CS, Link with formal education, Project management, Project sustainability, Reflections on science, Regulations and ethics, Research design and methods, and

Transferability. From the 128 individual resource needs identified, the following needs themes were most prevalent and most wanted (Figure 5):

- Communication (11.9%)
- Engagement (10.7%)
- Data quality and standards (8.3%)
- Introduction to citizen science (6.5%)
- Impact (6.5%)

2.3.1 Needs themes focus by stakeholder group

Further to identifying needs themes, it was also of interest to identify tendencies and prevalences within the different stakeholder groups that were consulted to identify resource needs (citizen science experts and practitioners via expert consultation, the wider CS community via the online survey, and funders and decision makers concerned with CS via the SwafS call text).

The CS expert group stressed resource needs and gaps around the topics of **communication, impact, data quality and standards**, and the **evaluation of CS**, followed in equal terms by transferability, engagement and instructables (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Needs themes focus of citizen science expert group

The wider CS practitioner community focused on needs related to **communication, engagement, the link with formal education, research design and methods** as well as **best practices**, followed by data quality and standards and project management (Figure 7).

Online survey with wider citizen science community (n=102)

Figure 7: Needs themes focus of wider citizen science practitioner community

SwafS call text (n=12)

Figure 8: Needs themes focus of funders (EC)

The funders and decision makers with a link to CS are most concerned about resources on **data quality and standards** as well as the topic of **engagement** (Figure 8).

2.3.1 Link between audiences and themes

Sometimes, specific audiences were named in relation to a needed resource for a particular theme (both topic and type-related). Table 2 provides an overview of the link between audiences and resources needed.

Table 2: Link between audiences and resource needs

Themes / Audience*	R/S	CS P	CSt	C	T	A	J	F	PM	NS
Best practices	x	x			x			x	x	
Co-creation										x
Communication	x	x		x			x			
CS stories										x
Data quality and standards	x	x	x							x
Empowerment			x		x	x				x
Engagement	x	x		x						x
Evaluation of CS	x									x
Event planning										x
Impact	x			x						x
Instructables	x	x			x			x	x	x
Introduction to CS	x		x	x			x	x		x
Link with formal education					x					x
Project management	x		x		x					x
Project sustainability	x							x	x	x
Reflections on science			x	x						x
Regulations and ethics										x
Research design and methods			x							x
Transferability	x				x	x				x

x - audience named more than once in relation to the resource theme, **x** - audience named more than once for an overall high-in-demand resource theme (see above). *R/S=Researchers / scientists, CS P=Citizen science practitioners, CSt=Citizen scientists, C=Citizens, T=Teachers, A=Activists, J=Journalists, F=Funders, PM=Policy makers, NS=Not specified

2.3.2 Links between resource types, topics and audiences

Sometimes, audiences were specifically named in relation to a needed resource for a specific topic and/or for a specific type of resource. Table 3 highlights, where specified, 1) audiences named to be in need of which type of resource, as well as 2) which type of resources are seen as needed for which topics, whether or not an audience was identified.

Table 3: Link between resource types, topics and audiences

INSTRUCTABLES on (topic)...	Resources needed for (audience)...
Topic not specified	Researchers/scientists, CS practitioners, funders, policy makers, teachers
Communication	N/A
Empowerment	N/A
CS link with formal education	N/A
Transferability	N/A
BEST PRACTICES on (topic)...	Resources needed for (audience)...
Topic not specified	Researchers/scientists , CS practitioners, funders, policy makers, teachers
Co-creation	N/A
Communication	N/A
Engagement	N/A
Impact	N/A
Research design and methods	N/A
INTRODUCTION TO CS, considering (topic)...	Resources needed for (audience)...
Topic not specified	Citizens, funders
Communication	Researchers/scientists (primary audience), journalists (secondary audience)
Engagement	Citizens
Empowerment	Citizen scientists
Impact	Citizens
Project management	Citizen scientists
Research design and methods	Citizen scientists
Transferability	Researchers/scientists

2.3.3 Specific resource needs

To understand how resource needs can be met by available resources, it is necessary to zoom from a broader picture back in and look at the individual and specific needs. Appendix 4 presents a comprehensive overview of individual resource needs clustered around needs themes, and based on individual needs identified. Some of them were slightly adjusted from the original formulations for better readability.

2.4 Needs summary

The analysis of resource needs based on three input sources makes clear that the resource needs of the citizen science community are diverse, specific and context dependent. There are, however, a few topics and types of resources that appear to be needed more generally. These are (1) resources on the topic of “communication” in CS, especially for researchers and scientists, and with a focus on instructables, i.e. resources that provide step-by-step and how-to guidance; (2) resources on the topic of “data quality and standards”, for a broad, non-specified audience as well as the researchers / scientists, CS practitioners and citizen scientists groups; (3) resources on the topic of “engagement”, especially for CS practitioners; (4) resources on the topic of “impact”, including best practice examples generally as well as for researchers/scientists and citizens specifically; and (5) resources that provide an “introduction on CS”, particularly for researchers/scientists and citizens.

In addition to these majority and generalisable needs, we also see some very specific and single “outlier” needs, that relate to specific audiences and contexts. These include, e.g., bottom-up resources for activists to apply citizen science techniques, resources for teachers to be able to integrate CS in the classroom, and resources for scientists/researchers from fields that are new to citizen science and less linked with the citizen science tradition.

Limitations

Understanding audience needs is an ongoing process and never complete as needs change and evolve. For example, the needs gathering and analysis happened before the COVID-19 crisis, which puts a limitation on the up-to-dateness or completeness of the formulated needs. The crisis has changed the CS landscape in several ways and many, including the EU-Citizen.Science project, have responded to e.g., the need for resources and activities to do from home. At the same time, the longer-term effect of the crisis on CS more generally remains uncertain. The attempt of the EU-Citizen.Science project is to iterate and stay aware of the needs and their nuances over time, through community engagement and feedback mechanisms, and to address the needs where possible within the capabilities of such a project. Where it is not possible to directly address the

needs, we develop strategies or approaches that can help to address them within a larger network and longer-term context.

2.5 Needs themes glossary

Once identified, these needs themes were used as metadata fields and as a filtering option for citizen science resources uploaded to the EU-Citizen.Science online platform.

We developed an initial resource needs theme glossary to be able to better describe the link between the needs and actual resources that could meet the needs, and to describe in more detail the type of resources that would qualify under each needs based theme. The glossary was developed through an iterative process that included glossary formulation, practical testing of the glossary by using it to guide resource collection and clustering as well as the adaptation of formulations based on feedback from the testing. As such, this descriptive table (Table 4) outlines the initial opportunity space of possible resources, stemming from the emergent needs themes.

Table 4: Glossary of resource needs themes

Resource needs theme	Description
Best practices	Resources that provide well-tested methodologies or tools that have been successfully implemented and that are also well-documented; also includes reviews and articles about well tested methodologies or tools that have been successfully implemented and can serve as examples for others.
Co-creation	Resources that provide and/or analyse methods for collaborative design, creation and development in CS; can range from platforms like Github to templates to specific group facilitation methods for co-creation.
Communication	Resource that provide tools and approaches for communication in CS; can address communication strategies to reach different stakeholder and target audiences, tools (for how) to set up a communication campaign; descriptions and guidelines for different forms of communication (e.g., storytelling, visualisations, videos, text, images, diagrams, etc); analysis of communication in CS and links to science communication.
Citizen science stories	Resources that offer insights that may not regularly be covered in CS case studies, or other forms of project overviews, e.g. personal stories about people's motivations, feelings or experiences in CS (e.g., an Instagram account of a CS project, that regularly provides photos and snap-shot experiences of volunteers).
Data quality and standards	Resources that offer insights, methods and tools on how to address data quality (e.g. how to reach and describe desired data quality levels) and data standards (how to work with and implement existing data standards, how to create new standards) in CS.
Empowerment	Resources that provide methods or tools to specifically enable certain audiences and groups to take part in CS, that would otherwise be excluded and where CS provides a means for these groups to be heard and their needs and problems to be recognised; resources that address the value added and added impact of CS and CS data to an existing

	cause or activity; also, resources that specifically address how to kick-start of CS projects from scratch in challenging contexts or environments (e.g. when faced with regulatory or social restrictions).
Engagement	Resources that provide approaches or tools (for how) to engage diverse audiences in CS; also includes reports or evaluations on audience and stakeholder engagement in CS.
Evaluation of citizen science	Resources that provide insight, tools and/or methods to evaluate CS projects; i.e. that help define and monitor targets, indicators and different success metrics.
Event planning	Resources that provide insights, tools and/or guidelines for event planning and implementation as well as event communication in CS.
Impact	Resources that provide insight, tools and/or methods to understand, document and communicate impact in CS; can include tools, instructions and reflections on how to define and trace impact, how to define impact indicators, and how to measure and document them, how to communicate them, how to make impact assessment comprehensible and transparent.
Instructables	Any resources that come in form of an instruction that can be followed in a step-by-step fashion (e.g., protocols, tutorials, apps with forms to fill); resources that aim at providing clear descriptions for how to implement something.
Introduction to citizen science	Resources that provide an introduction to CS, characterised by providing a general overview; can be to theory of CS, or practice and application; tools that help understand the basics of CS, or that help get started with CS.
Link with formal education	Resources that address the link between CS and formal education, e.g. tools and resources for integrating CS into school curricula, lesson plans for CS projects in schools, CS toolkits for schools and instructions on how to do CS in class, best practices and experiences on doing CS in schools, reports and evaluations of CS and CS learning in schools etc.; can also include tools for doing CS that work well in the classroom.
Project management	Resources that provide specific insights, methods and/or tools for project management of CS projects, focusing on the practice of coordinating and leading the work of a team to achieve goals and meet success criteria at a specified time; can include aspects such as budget and staff planning and monitoring, team coordination and team communication, collaborative work and conflict resolution, time planning and progress monitoring of tasks, planning, launching and implementation of different project stages etc.
Project sustainability	Resources that provide insight, tools and/or approaches to make projects last long(er), or how to ensure uptake and exploitation of results, or how to facilitate transition to new projects.
Reflections on science	Resources that offer reflections or methods for reflecting on science and the scientific method more generally; can include how to question and remain critical of scientific findings, introduction to science, evidence-based approaches, biases in science, uncertainties in science etc.
Regulations and ethics	Resources that offer insights, methods and tools to understand, address and integrate regulations and ethics in CS (e.g., GDPR compliance, ethical research, open science etc).

Research design and methods	Resources that address the specificities of research design and research methods in CS; includes description and/or analysis of approaches for research design and research methods development in CS, potentially covering all stages of the research process; also includes tools and resources used as part of conducting the research; depending on the research objective, specific tools can include tools for data collection, sampling, chats, forums, etc.
Transferability	Resources that provide insight, reflections, tools and/or approaches to applying CS methodologies/tools developed and tested in one domain or scientific field to be used in another; or to implementing CS in new fields entirely, where the application of CS is new and unprecedented.

3 Resource status

The next step towards the identification of gaps in CS resources on the EU-Citizen.Science platform, was to take full account of the existing resources available to the citizen science community on the platform. Stock was taken on July 14, 2020, taking into account all resources that had been uploaded and accessible to the public prior to and on that date.

3.1 Citizen science resources on EU-Citizen.Science platform

The term “CS resources” used by the EU-Citizen.Science project and the online platform was defined in detail as part of the definition for quality criteria for resources on the platform. The full development process as well as the quality criteria are documented in the *Framework Report Describing Criteria and Rationale for Sharing and Selecting State of the art Citizen Science Resources* (Fraisl et al., 2020).

Based on this report, the EU-Citizen.Science platform currently defines CS resources as “resources and practices that could be used for help and support in the context of CS”. These resources can help an individual, a project or an organisation to understand, implement and evaluate CS and CS practices, and demonstrate the value of CS to different audiences. CS resources are further divided into the following main **categories**: (i) tools, (ii) guidelines, (iii) training resources and (iv) other materials. In total, three main (i-iii) and seven sub-categories for other materials (iv) are currently used to differentiate CS resources on the EU-Citizen.Science platform:

- **Tools** are “any software or hardware to help perform a particular task or work in CS initiatives (e.g. water quality equipment, air quality sensors, etc.)”.
- **Guidelines** are “a set of rules and instructions that could be helpful in designing, implementing or evaluating CS or initiatives relevant to citizen science. Guidelines are written texts such as reports, deliverables, briefings, etc.”.

- **Training resources** are “some form of instructional material in relation to CS often related to ‘how to do’ citizen science. Some examples include MOOCs, (online) workshops, webinars, gamified training, quizzes, etc.”.
- **Other Materials** are “resources” other than “tools”, “guidelines” and “training resources” that are about or relevant to citizen science”. Other materials address a broad spectrum of resources, hence they were divided further in seven sub-categories:
 - **Libraries:** An organised set of resources such as databases, repositories, toolkits and toolboxes that bring together relevant documents for a particular purpose in CS initiatives.
 - **Scientific publications:** Publications where scientific knowledge on CS is shared.
 - **Websites:** Websites, platforms, webpages where citizen science related content is published.
 - **Reports:** A document that presents information on citizen science or on topics relevant to CS.
 - **Audio:** Any resource with sound that includes CS related content such as podcasts, audio books, radio broadcasts, etc.
 - **Visuals:** Any resource that includes visual content such as videos, diagrams, figures, illustrations, etc.
 - **Miscellaneous:** Any resource that does not fit the definitions of the first 6 subcategories under “other materials”.

This categorisation marks the starting point for resource collection on the EU-Citizen.Science platform and will iteratively develop over time, based on considerations gained through operating the platform, a better understanding of the user experience, as well as the intention to align to international standards for resource definitions.

3.2 Resources online on EU-Citizen.Science on 14 July, 2020

The EU-Citizen.Science platform went public in its BETA version on 6 April, 2020, offering an initial set of CS resources to the community, collected by the project partners.

By 14 July, 2020, 82 resources were available on the EU-Citizen.Science platform. Of those, 61 were in English, six in Spanish, five in German, three in Hungarian, two in French, two in Dutch, two in Italian and one in Estonian. When uploading resources to the platform, it is mandatory to assign a resource to a particular category, as outlined above. The following three categories were the most prevalent: 35.5% of resources were categorised as Guidelines, 16% as Training resources, and 11% as Scientific Publications (Figure 9).

Resource categories

Figure 9: Distribution of available resources across resource categories

While it is possible to assign resources to one resource category only, they can be assigned to more than one resource theme during the uploading process of the platform. Of the total number of resources (82), most of them (60) are listed under more than one resource theme (Figure 10). The highest number of resources are available for topics related to engagement, the introduction to CS, research design and methods as well as data quality and standards and communication.

Themes covered in resources

Figure 10: Distribution of available resources across resource themes

Almost half of the resources (37) are believed to serve as best practice resources. Considering the thematic clustering within resource categories we see, for example, that within the “Guidelines” category the topical areas (as opposed to type-specific resources such as best practices or instructables) with the largest representation are research design and methods, communication, and

guidelines on data quality and standards, engagement, evaluation of citizen science, introduction to CS and project management (cf. Table 5).

Table 5: Number of resources available in total per category and number of resources available per theme

Themes / Categories	Tools	Guide-lines	Training resources	Libraries	Scientific pub	Websites	Reports	Audio	Visuals	Total
Number of resources	7	29	13	8	9	7	7	0	2	82
Best practices	3	15	6	4	5	0	3	0	1	37
Co-creation	5	2	2	1	0	1	2	0	0	13
Communication	2	7	2	1	2	1	3	0	0	18
CS stories	0	3	1	3	2	0	2	0	0	11
Data quality and standards	1	6	4	3	3	0	1	0	0	18
Empowerment	1	3	2	0	0	1	2	0	0	9
Engagement	5	6	6	3	0	5	3	0	0	28
Evaluation of CS	0	6	1	2	3	0	3	0	0	15
Event planning	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Impact	1	2	3	3	3	0	5	0	0	17
Instructables	0	9	6	1	0	1	0	0	0	17
Introduction to CS	0	6	8	4	4	1	1	0	0	24
Link with formal education	0	4	5	2	0	0	0	0	0	11
Project management	1	6	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	11
Project sustainability	1	2	4	1	0	0	0	0	1	9
Reflections on science	1	1	1	1	1	3	4	0	0	12
Regulations and ethics	0	5	0	3	1	0	2	0	0	11
Research design and methods	3	8	4	3	1	1	0	0	0	20
Transferability	1	3	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	6
Not specified	0	2	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	4

*Most prevalent needs themes (see section 2.3) are highlighted in grey.

Main insights

The status analysis of the resources online on EU-Citizen.Science first and foremost reflects the young age of the platform, in terms of total number of resources as well as resources across themes

and categories. Overall, we see a clear **overrepresentation of English language** resources. Likewise, other European languages are underrepresented, and many are not yet represented at all. There is a relatively balanced mix of resources available across categories, or types of resources (e.g., guidelines, training and other materials). However, **most resources** are put in the **guidelines** category, and there are **very few** available in the **tools** category. Several resources are assigned to **many themes**, which indicates that they likely cover a **broad thematic spectrum**. For some, it may also indicate that they are **only partially applicable** to the specific themes. Other resources are linked with **one theme only**. Likely they are **specific and fully applicable** to that theme.

Limitations

The analysis is based on a **snapshot** of the state of the resources on the EU-Citizen.Science on a given day (July 14, 2020), while the actual available resources constantly increase. Hence, this analysis is inherently out of date. Nonetheless, it helps to develop a better understanding of resource gaps to be able to better target resource sourcing activities. Furthermore, as described in section 2.5, the identified needs themes were used to inform a metadata field when uploading the resources and subsequently as a filtering option for resources on the EU-Citizen.Science platform. This process allows for an inherent **uncertainty and fuzziness of interpretation** when assigning themes to resources. This fuzziness may stem from a lack of clarity of the themes themselves, a shared understanding of their definitions as well as explicit or hidden goals of those uploading resources. Also, some uploaders may treat the themes conservatively, others very broadly. This difference may also create confusion with platform users.

Above all, these insights can help to inform how to **improve the user experience** regarding resources online, while still addressing resource needs and providing meaningful themes. For example, limiting the amount of themes that can be assigned to a resource could improve categorisation under themes and make sure that the most relevant and most applicable themes are chosen. The actual findability of resources depends to a large degree on users assigning themes and keywords in a deliberate and robust way as well as specific system features to allow for comprehensive discoverability of relevant resources.

4 Resource gaps

4.1 Gap analysis model

To find and close relevant resource gaps on EU-Citizen.Science, we considered different ways to identify gaps by looking at several gap analysis models. Some models consider different perception, assumption and expectation levels as well as translation and communication gaps between them (Parasuraman et al., 1985; Winch et al., 1998). Other models focus more on the overall context and

process, comparing state of the art and visions across multiple dimensions, as well as considering the refinement of gaps before taking actions to close them, often within an iterative process (Kamtsiou et al., 2007; Pucihar, 2007). Others reduce the complexity to a minimum, comparing desired vs. existing states and outlining actions to close the gap (Brabcová et al., 2016). The models have in common that the gaps are placed in between different states and emerge where expectations, needs or desired states are not met with an available service or resource. To identify resource gaps within EU-Citizen.Science, we acknowledge and take into consideration the multiple perception and translation gaps where possible, as highlighted in Figure 11. These include gaps such as:

- GAP 1 - Perception gap: A gap between what resources are actually needed or expected and what one thinks is needed or expected.
- GAP 2 - Translation or communication gap: A gap emerging in the process of communicating a specific resource need or a perceived need of others; as well as communicating or facilitating the availability of a resource to meet the needs.
- GAP 3 - Delivery gap: A gap between identified needs and the actual delivery to meet the needs.
- GAP 4 - Experience gap: A gap between what resources are expected and what is perceived to be available.
- GAP 5 - Availability gap: A gap between what is expected/needed and what is available.

Figure 11: Gap analysis model for resource gap analysis on EU-Citizen.Science

In the main gap analysis, we focus on GAP 5, the availability gap between expected resources and actual available resources online. We take into account the identified resource needs (see section 2), and compare them with the available resources on the EU-Citizen.Science platform on July 14, 2020. We also consider explicit and implicit assumptions stemming from the EU-Citizen.Science project goals and context on what kind of resources *should* be provided to the community. These include expectations that resources should be provided for multiple stakeholders and audiences, have a specific focus on practitioners and their needs, be applicable to and/or reflect a European context with regional differences, be of high quality as well as state-of-the-art. The assumption is also that it is desirable to provide access to several and slightly complementary resources to meet the needs to allow for resource diversity and to offer selection options that can cater to the different user contexts.

4.2 Gap analysis

The gap analysis revolved around four main questions:

- What is the quality assessment of the resources?
- What is the availability in different languages?
- Are resources available for the identified needs?
- Are the resources fully or only partially applicable or suitable?

4.2.1 Quality

Regarding the quality of resources on the EU-Citizen.Science platform, the project has worked towards establishing transparent, inclusive and operational quality criteria to be used as part of a resource moderation process (see Fraisl et al., 2020). This way, the project ensures that good quality resources are published on the EU-Citizen.Science platform and no gaps should arise due to unsatisfactory quality. By July 14, 2020, very few resources (8) uploaded on the platform had to be excluded, or their publication put on hold. Resources put on hold were mainly subject to further clarification on how they relate to and can benefit citizen science. Due to the deliberate quality process, **no considerable quality gaps** can be identified at this point. In addition, a community-based quality check and rating system has been implemented, which will further support high quality of resources as well as give more about their usefulness and applicability.

4.2.2 Language

If we look at the availability of resources in different languages, it becomes clear that the EU-Citizen.Science platform currently delivers to an international audience, one that is used to English as a working language. At the same time, the EU-Citizen.Science project aims to address

the cultural and contextual diversity within Europe and to deliver resources to local and regional communities and practitioners as well as to international actors. Hence, the underrepresentation of European languages on the platform to date represents a **significant language gap**.

The resource themes identified as being most needed or desired by various stakeholders, such as resources on the topics of communication, engagement, data quality and standards, introduction to CS as well as on the topic of impact of citizen science can serve as an initial focal point to start to close this resource gap. Furthermore, additional work could be done to better understand more localised and regional needs, taking advantage of the wide network of national and regional citizen science associations and groups within the EU-Citizen.Science project.

The analysis of language gaps has one limitation. The available resources were not analysed for their readability scores (e.g., using tests such as Flesch-Kincaid, Gunning Fox etc.), which may indicate additional gaps related to the resource's suitability i.e. how easy or hard they are to read and understand for different audiences.

4.2.3 Availability

Apart from language availability, other considerations on resource availability are important. If we look at the general availability of resources, all needs themes are covered by a number of resources, which would indicate no gaps in terms of provided topics or types of resources. However, if we look at the available resource categories (Table 6), we see that hardly any “tools” are available overall (7), tools are missing entirely for many themes and some tools are generic and fall under several themes. For example, looking at the theme “data quality and standards”, we count 18 resource entries in total, amongst which six are “guidelines” and only one is indicated as a “tool”. This tool¹, on the other hand, is linked to nine other themes, such as project management, co-creation, or project sustainability.

Furthermore, the EU-Citizen.Science project follows an inclusive approach and aims to offer resources that are enabling and provide guidance to a diverse audience and different stakeholder groups and that satisfy a range of expectations. Hence, very specific, as well as “outlier”, resource needs for particular and potentially new audiences, despite falling outside the mainstream needs, are just as relevant to consider. Let's look at a specific resource need, such as: “video interviews with participants to explain their feelings with participation [in citizen science] and their needs”. No such resource, or a similar one, is currently available on the EU-Citizen.Science platform. Also, the platform does not currently offer any resources “for activist groups to do citizen science and combine political objectives with science”.

¹ SPOTTERON: <https://eu-citizen.science/resource/66>

The findability of resources on the platform is an additional aspect that can support or inhibit the actual availability of a resource to the user community. For example, currently, it is not possible to filter the resources by audience. When searching for a resource on the platform, e.g., using an audience specific search term such as “scientists”, “researchers”, or “activists”, presumably wanting to find resources for these audiences, no results are returned, unless these terms are used in the title of the resource. Also, if we look for tools for linking CS with formal education, no results are returned. If we search for “schools”, we find *Tree Tools for Schools*² a compendium of interactive activities and other practical tools for teachers.

Hence, as shown in the examples above, regarding the availability of resources, **gaps can be identified both in terms of general availability as well as specific availability**. Furthermore, the analysis reveals that the mechanisms of findability of available resources on the platform can be improved.

4.2.4 Applicability/Suitability

To further identify resource gaps and understand the resources available, we examined the suitability, applicability and specificity of a resource in relation to a needs theme, target audience or regional context. For some needs, targeted resources may exist, while other needs may only be addressed partially as part of a summary, larger content package or toolbox, for one specific audience or only within a specific regional/national context. Gaps emerge where partial suitability and applicability can be identified. For example, six “guidelines” are available for the theme “data quality and standards” (Figure 12).

Considering them in more detail, it becomes apparent that two of them are general introductions to CS that also touch on data quality issues more generally, two of them are directed at policy and two are guidelines for practitioners placed within the US context. Hence, the following critical gap can be identified: There are currently no practical guidelines on data quality and standards available on the EU-Citizen.Science platform for citizen science practitioners in the European context. When looking at the resources listed under the theme of “communication”, a similar situation emerges. Of the 17 resources listed, most are general introductions to CS that also touch on the topic of communication or reports on CS projects. Only two of the resources specifically address the topic of communication, however in very different ways. One resource provides a communication guide for practitioners³, the other is a scientific publication⁴, discussing terminology in and of CS and why it matters on a meta-level.

² Tree Tools for Schools: <https://eu-citizen.science/resource/18>

³ Communication in Citizen Science - A practical guide to communication and engagement in citizen science: <https://eu-citizen.science/resource/52>

⁴ Citizen Science Terminology Matters: Exploring Key Terms: <https://eu-citizen.science/resource/31>

Figure 12: Resources on EU-Citizen.Science marked as “guidelines” under the theme “data quality and standards”

Suitability and applicability gaps are the most complex gaps, as they largely depend on actual context and how resources can be put to practice. The bottom-up rating and review system implemented on the platform allows the community to share experiences and provide tangible insights into the practical value of resources, over and above this desktop gap analysis. Nonetheless, these examples illustrate that when considering more detailed aspects of resource applicability and suitability, **several suitability gaps** become evident.

4.3 The main gaps

The following list summarises the findings of the resource gap analysis and highlights the most important gaps, translating them to “citizen science resources missing on the EU-Citizen.Science platform”. There are two main reasons why these resources may not yet be available on EU-Citizen.Science, or why they appear to be unavailable. Either *the desired resources do not yet exist in a suitable and usable format*, and/or they have *yet to be successfully sourced and/or made accessible and findable through the EU-Citizen.Science platform*.

The most important gaps:

- Resources **in multiple European languages**, starting with **Introductions to CS**: the aim should be to provide an introduction to CS in most of the European languages.
- Resources on **most wanted topics** in CS, **specifically addressing**:
 - Communication
 - Engagement
 - Data quality and standards
 - Impact of CS

A minimum of two high-quality resources should be available that specifically, not broadly, address these most wanted themes.

- Resources that have tangible value and are **of use for the implementation of citizen science**
 - Operational, adaptable and well tested **“tools”, for all topics**
 - **Guidelines** for specific topics with a **European focus**
 - Co-creation and co-design
 - Communication - of CS generally and of CS results specifically
 - Engagement and volunteer management
 - Impact - how to frame and capture
 - Implementation of data quality and standards
 - Regulations and ethics - how to conform and deploy
 - Evaluation of CS
 - Project management
 - Project sustainability
- **Special interest resources** that target specific needs of certain stakeholder and audience groups; more resources should be provided, specifically targeting:
 - Schools, teachers and school children
 - Activist groups, NGOs/CSOs and bottom-up initiatives
 - Scientists/researchers from non-traditional CS fields (e.g., social sciences, humanities, arts, culture) to help them adapt and adopt the CS approach
 - Policy makers
- **Stories about CS** and **reflections on science**, highlighting people’s motivations and experiences in doing CS, stories of impact of CS on different levels, as well as more philosophical considerations about science and the methods, limitations, challenges and rewards of knowledge production.

In addition, Table 6 presents more specific resources gaps based on individual needs identified (Appendix 4). For the identification of a gap, the following rationale was applied: If one resource was available on the EU-Citizen.Science platform to meet a specific need, it was still considered a gap. If more than one resource were available, it was not considered a gap. When needed resources fell under more than one theme, or were very similar to each other, only one of them was kept on the list. Some of the gaps were adjusted from the original formulations for better readability.

Table 6: Specific resource gaps, or “resources missing” on the EU-Citizen.Science platform per theme

Resource needs theme	Specific resource gaps
Best practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Best practices for how to share and visualize data results > Best practices for co-design of projects and co-design of technology > Best practices regarding different participative methods
Co-creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Co-creation guidelines for including the public to scientists
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > How to publish results in science and the popular media > How to write a policy brief and communicate relevance of research to policy makers > How to present data to local politicians and creating green papers > Guide on how to manage communication [...] in CS > How to understand audiences and channels to reach them (and what for) > Media dossiers, fact check guides for journalists > How to share and visualise data results for a broad audience and real world examples
CS stories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Motivations of citizen scientists and academic researchers for participating/conducting CS projects > Interviews with CS coordinators to explain their experience > Interviews with participants to explain their feelings with participation and their needs > Champion stories of local communities > Policy impact stories
Data quality and standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Data quality standards > Existing data gathering/quality assurance tools and data repositories > Fun video to better understand data quality assurance > Quality assurance tools and methods > How to encourage volunteers to submit even when they didn't find what they're looking for (importance of null data and submitting zeros)
Empowerment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Video for activists groups to do citizen science and how to combine political objectives with science > Tools to affect change with a social justice focus
Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Written guide on recruiting and supporting participants/citizen scientists (including diversity) > Gender inclusive engagement for citizen science experiments > Involvement of underrepresented audiences > More information on attracting people to the projects > Best practices regarding different participative methods > Empirical methods and respective involvement plans > How to ensure balanced participation of citizens (e.g. regardless of background, gender and age)

	> How to keep volunteers motivated and responding to their questions
Evaluation of CS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > How to measure intangibles, e.g. PEG, key metric vs. vanity metrics > Evaluation and monitoring tool > More on how to measure success metrics in CS projects (qualitative and quantitative)
Event planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Event guidelines (including e.g., code of conduct) > Guidelines and material to organise physical workshops for participants
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > How to make research relevant for policy > Articles about impact of citizen science to civil society > Written guide or audio toolkit on "pathways to impact" statements to include in research proposals > How to reach decision makers and design projects in a way that they can have policy impact > Documentation of impacts of citizen science projects, especially societal impacts > Podcast and/or video to give the public the whole view of citizen science projects, (with the impact of Citizen Science in every day) [...] > How to bridge citizen science findings with policymakers/local government's actions
Instructables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Manual on how to start a citizen science lab > How to create good YouTube videos > Plug-and-play templates and software tools generated by the community to easily create (project-specific) resources > A short series of videos with how-to's for each stage of citizen science development and implementation > Practical tools: action plans, checklists etc.
Introduction to CS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Information for funders of CS on what is special and unique about CS > How to start considering a citizen science approach for researchers to address their own research needs > A brief for academics to address scepticism and how to view CS as an opportunity > Text and diagrams for orientation on on existing citizen science technologies and communities
Link with formal education	> Tailored written resources for school teachers, including what citizen science can do for them and how it meets their needs
Project management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > How to coordinate (with) educators/teacher > Data management tools and common back office tools for citizen science initiatives > Resources for project management > Guidance on the use of reliable third party data management systems and tools > Time management to better balance contribution to different tasks > How to plan/organize/manage training for citizen scientists > Guidelines and material to organise physical workshops for participants
Project sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The funding, organisational and practical aspects of sustaining long-term projects > Text, video for researchers, policymakers and funders on how to think about the project beyond a single funding cycle > Business model planning for sustainability

Reflections on science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Something that explains what science is with examples of good and bad science > Resources that allow citizens to understand the political contexts in which research is happening and learn how to judge different kinds of research > Resources that allow citizen scientists to question existing research, and develop alternatives > Resources that make citizens understand that research is often inconclusive and hard to interpret > Resources that allow citizens to understand why science is such a wonderful and arduous task
Regulations and ethics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Guide to EU data policy > Privacy assurance in citizen science measurements > Guidance for handling private data (including names, e-mail addresses, location, images etc.), especially under GDPR > Text on ethics and legal questions, especially regarding projects with minors > Resources on challenges in managing the ethics of citizen science and how to tackle them > How to recognise the work of citizens participating in citizen science initiatives
Research design and methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Resources to help with methodological development of citizen science questions > How to formulate a research question for participative research > Best practice especially regarding methodology > How to define a suitable research question > How to choose the optimum methodologies
Transferability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Support for people who want to incorporate CS in European Training Network proposals/projects > Collective activities for CS in Humanities, Humanities within education, social sciences > Resources for citizen social science, with more of an arts/interdisciplinary focus > How to make CS transferable in other domains, e.g. how to launch CS projects in areas such as language learning and teaching, or in user engagement in creation of resources in their own language > Resources on citizen science in arts and culture

5 Conclusion and next steps: Opportunities to close the gaps

Given the analysis above, we conclude that there are still considerable resource gaps on the EU-Citizen.Science platform at this stage, and clear strategies are needed to close the main gaps. To follow up on the gaps identification, a gaps assessment will help to prioritise gaps and to highlight which of the identified gaps, both broad and individual, will need specific attention in order to close them. Furthermore, both the categorisation and filtering/searching of resources on the platform pose a challenge and need further attention to improve the user experience, to make resources accessible and findable as well as to increase the specificity and applicability of resources to certain resource themes.

5.1 Collective ideation

To identify a range of opportunities to close resource gaps, we tapped into the collective intelligence of the project partners across Europe during the annual plenary project meeting which

was held online on June 18-19, 2020. We used an interactive session format which was attended by 18 project members to collaboratively generate ideas from which distinct pathways could be derived.

5.2 Opportunities to close resource gaps

The following section outlines a range of possible actions and opportunities to inform next steps and future work undertaken in *Task 3.2 Collating state of the art in citizen science: tools, guidelines and materials*. These opportunities also link with other WPs, such as *WP2 Platform, Community and Network Building* or *WP5 - Training Needs Assessment, Creation and Delivery* to support closing the identified gaps in resources on the EU-Citizen.Science platform.

Actions for closing resource gaps have been identified by the project partners around the following six opportunity areas:

- (1) Project specific actions to close resource gaps;
- (2) Mobilisation actions via the EU-Citizen.Science platform, community building and outreach, including the integration of the Citizen Science Translation Hub (CSTH) into the EU-Citizen.Science platform;
- (3) External funding opportunities;
- (4) Events for resource creation and sourcing;
- (5) Activation of ECSA network, partner networks, other working groups/networks and projects;
- (6) Link with national/international platforms and associations.

Ideally, opportunities within these areas can be actioned by the EU-Citizen.Science project in the short term (within the next 6 months) or in the medium term (by the end of the project funding period, December 2021). The following subsections (5.2.1 - 5.2.6) describe the six opportunity areas in more detail.

5.2.1 Project specific actions to close resource gaps

Project specific actions to close resource gaps are specific activities taken by the EU-Citizen.Science partners as part of the project work plan to continue to directly create, source and upload specific resources.

Short term - The following actions can be taken in the short term to gradually increase the number of resources on the platform and to start closing the gaps:

- Action links with WPs on training, policy engagement and linking with other EU-funded RIA projects. This will help to ensure that identified resource gaps are considered in the

design and production of the training modules (WP5, see report *D5.2 Design of training activities and materials*) and the planned toolkit development for policy makers (WP4). Raising awareness on resource gaps through networking activities with other projects (WP1) can further help to jointly close the gaps.

- Establish a working group within the project, dedicated to address the resource gaps through external sourcing. Activities of the working group could focus on:
 - Highlighting known resources that would help close the gaps; using the resource needs themes structure and find a minimum of two "best" resources for each of the themes (e.g., 'seminal work' or 'best guidelines' for how to handle data quality), keeping specific audiences in mind; actively reaching out to identified audiences and groups, according to their strategic importance to the success of the platform (see report *D2.1 Stakeholder Mapping*).
 - Identifying and reaching out to known projects that may produce suitable resources.
 - Scanning programs of (previous/upcoming) CS conferences for workshops or presentations on tools and resources and contact conveners.

Medium term - The following actions could be taken in the medium term to gradually increase the number of resources on the platform and to start closing the gaps:

- Establish a working group to jointly produce selected resources, and invite the community to join the co-creation group; benefits include co-authorship and the existence of needed resources; consider using the WeObserve Communities of Practice or the ECSA Working Groups as examples or vehicles for this.
- Often, valuable and practical information is hidden in academic papers and project reports. The EU-Citizen.Science project could provide support to other projects on how to turn project reports or scientific papers into a "guideline" style resource.

5.2.2 Actions via EU-Citizen.Science platform, community outreach and building

Actions via the EU-Citizen.Science platform, community building and outreach include the integration of the CSTH tool and focus on the mobilisation of the wider CS community to contribute existing resources to the EU-Citizen.Science platform. The following are opportunities to support closing the resource gaps via the platform and will be jointly considered for their feasibility and are subject to the scope and plans of WP2.

Short term - In the short term, several platform related actions could be taken as part of the wider community engagement to reach audiences and increase resource contributions, e.g.:

- Create a “most wanted” resources list on the EU-Citizen.Science platform, and publish an open call for these resources under specific topics, quarterly, or per month.
 - This call can also be included in the newsletter that is created and shared amongst RIA projects.
 - Consider allocating funds for some form of recognition for a resource submitted based on an open call (e.g. ECSA membership for a year).
- Create a button, such as ‘not found?’, and a feedback form where users can indicate what they are looking for.

Medium term - More elaborate platform features could be implemented in the medium term to help establish processes where the community could take ownership of requesting and sourcing relevant resources.

- Use the community forum on the platform to address resource gaps by creating a sub-forum dedicated to closing resource gaps, or via making ‘resource requests’. Users could post requests for resources, others could comment and/or direct to relevant resources.
- Implement a “signposting” feature for specific topics where users can indicate other projects/resources in those domains. Linking best practices and resources on a specific topic across projects may support other projects to increase their impact and reach, further strengthening the learning among projects.
- Provide specific information to project/resource owners of the platform, such as statistics on project/resource visits, and, via the same channel, highlight and ask for resource contributions for identified gaps.

Citizen Science Translation Hub

Language availability has been identified as a main resource gap on the EU-Citizen.Science platform. To address this gap, actions will be taken to integrate the CSTH into the EU-Citizen.Science platform. The CSTH was initially developed as part of the DITOs project⁵. Its purpose is to crowdsource translations of useful CS material (websites, policy briefs, handbooks, instruction kits, etc.) into more languages - usually languages other than English.

Two workflows and roles characterise the CSTH:

- 1) *The writer*: A CS project, individual, institution, trainer or other disseminator of information, who has produced some useful material. The writer e-mails the CSTH manager with a copy of or link to the text (or video). The CSTH manager then creates a plain text version, which is

⁵ <https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/ditos>

uploaded to the site. Each project that has submitted a text is given a separate subpage containing some basic information about that project and the text (language, word count, subject area, style, etc). Any writer who submits text agrees to host it on their website alongside a notice to thank the translators.

- 2) *The translator*: Anyone who speaks more than one language, and is interested in CS, can visit the website, browse the subpage to choose a text of interest, and download it. They also inform the Csth manager that they are working on the translation, and into what language. They send in the translation. The Csth manager then puts an announcement on the website that they seek a proofreader. Proofreaders check the work for scientific and language errors and for style, then they send their review copy. The Csth manager then moves the document into a “completed translations” area and sends a copy to the writer, who makes the new translation available to use.

Translation is a professional skill which is most often paid for. Hence, it is important to reward and support volunteer translators in whatever way is possible. This is currently done by providing links to information about CS and translation which they might find useful, and a discussion forum where they can support each other and the network and suggest improvements. They also receive public thanks for their work by the Csth manager and the original writer.

The Csth is currently hosted on a Wix platform as a small website⁶. Before incorporating it to the EU-Citizen.Science platform, it will stay on this platform in order to test and learn more about the process and to understand where improvements could be made. Once implemented on EU-Citizen.Science, the Csth can be used to make useful resources available for translation.

5.2.3 External funding

Additionally available, and specific national or EU-wide funding could further stimulate the creation of specific resources.

Medium term - Activities that help to tap into new funding opportunities for resource could be:

- Identifying existing funding opportunities that can support the development of new resources, as well as publishing and communicating these opportunities on EU-Citizen.Science.
- Formulating a brief to the EC and to national funding bodies, which can serve as a basis for (small) tenders to support the development of specific resources.

⁶ <https://citscitranlate.wixsite.com/citscitranlate>

5.2.4 Events for resource creation and sourcing

Events, both online and face-to-face, have also been identified as a possible means to create and source resources to close resource gaps.

Short term - The EU-Citizen.Science project could organise a webinar on CS resources, highlight the main gaps and involve the participants in an interactive exercise to collect specific resources they have found useful, then add these resources to the platform.

Medium term - In the medium term, other events and formats can provide opportunities to promote resource gathering on the platform:

- Events organised by EU-Citizen.Science partners, also as part of other projects, to reach out to a wider audience to promote resource gathering on the EU-Citizen.Science platform (e.g. a dedicated event at the ECSA conference, other conference, workshops etc.).
- A public EU-Citizen.Science event where citizen scientists are encouraged to record a short video or write a short blog post about their work and experience (e.g., “What I wish I had known when I started”).
- Each partner organisation could organise (online) workshops or sessions in their own countries, and/or support national networking events and workshops on CS to share and synthesise knowledge as well as to raise awareness about the EU-Citizen.Science platform and the opportunity to share resources.

5.2.5 Activate ECSA network, partner networks, other working groups/networks and projects

The wide partner network and linked networks of the EU-Citizen.Science consortium⁷ presents another opportunity to source resources and close resource gaps.

Short term - Short term actions taken by and involving all partners across the project, can include:

- Reaching out to national and local networks to collect resources, especially to collect resources in languages other than EN/FR/ESP etc.
- Include a call for specific topical resources in the joint RIA projects newsletter.
- Use upcoming WeObserve CoP meetings to ask participants for resource suggestions.

⁷ See e.g., the wide ECSA network: <https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/community/map>

Medium term - For the medium term, opportunities have been identified specifically around ECSA working groups, links with other projects as well as further tapping into an extended community.

ECSA working groups

- Encourage ECSA members to add resources on relevant topics, as a monthly task of an ECSA working group.
- Address specific ECSA working groups⁸, e.g. on “Sharing best practice and building capacity”, “Projects, data, tools, and technology”, for sourcing resources related to the focus of the working group (e.g., best practices, data quality and standards, empowerment etc.).
- Reach out to ECSA working groups with a call to develop a resource, or for the group to identify national projects that can develop a resource to be shared on the platform.

Projects and extended community

- Identify and contact other EU funded projects with a CS component (e.g., Life+ or Life Governance projects), to raise awareness of the platform as a resource for inspiration as well as a place to share their resources.
- Identify communities at EU level that are close to CS and could also contribute valuable resources (e.g., volunteering in libraries, archives, museums etc.).
- Identify and establish links with relevant university programmes (MSc and MA) to further support the development of resources and/or search for resources.
- Reach out to environmental justice groups that participated in the CitSci 2019 conference⁹.

5.2.6 Link with other citizen science platforms and associations

To link more closely with other dedicated CS platforms and associations internationally can, amongst other benefits, help source important CS resources. *Medium term* actions can include to:

- Link with national/international initiatives, e.g., facilitate the formation of a working group across national/international CS associations and platforms to address the exchange/integration of resources, as well as challenges of resource quality and moderation.
- Collaborate more closely with other associations and practitioners to understand which resources are currently under development, by e.g., the Citizen Science Association or the Australian Citizen Science Association, and see if they can be adjusted to the European context.

⁸ <https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/about-us>

⁹ <https://www.citizenscience.org/events/conferences/citsci2019/>

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Appendix 1 - Expert consultation

The following citizen science practitioners and experts were present at the expert consultation session during the EU-Citizen.Science proposal meeting in Berlin in February 2018 and contributed to the needs/gaps analysis exercise.

- Andrea Sforzi, Director of Museo di Storia Naturale della Maremma and ECSA BoD, Italy
- Barbara Kieslinger, Project Manager, Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (ZSI), Austria
- Gerid Hager, IIASA, Ecosystems Services and Management Program (ESM), Austria
- Gisela Wachinger, DIALOGIK - gemeinnützige Gesellschaft für Kommunikations- und Kooperationsforschung mbH, Germany
- Ivonne Jansen-Dings, Head of Programme, Waag Society, Netherlands.
- Janice Ansine, Senior Project Manager (Citizen Science), Faculty of Science, Technology, Engineering & Mathematics, The Open University, UK
- Jaume Piera, National Spanish Research Council
- John Harlin, Leysin American School and ECSA WG Learning and Education, Switzerland
- Joseph Roche, Assistant Professor of Science Education, Trinity College Dublin and Science Gallery, Ireland
- Lucy Robinson, Natural History Museum of London, UK
- Luigi Ceccaroni (Engagement & Science) and Wim Clymans (Research Manager), Earthwatch Institute, UK
- Maria Zolotonosa, Senior Project Manager, ECSITE, Belgium
- Markus Weisskopf, Wissenschaft im Dialog, Germany
- Michael Søgaard Jørgensen, Associate Professor, Department of Planning, Aalborg University, Denmark
- Muki Haklay, UCL, UK
- Pedro Russo, Leiden Observatory, Netherlands.
- Poppy Lakeman, OPAL Senior Coordinator, Centre for Environmental Policy, Imperial College London, UK
- Rosa Arias, Project Manager, Ibercivis Foundation, Spain
- Susanne Hecker, Academic Staff, German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv), Leipzig, Germany
- Wim Clymans (Research Manager), Earthwatch Institute, UK

From ECSA and MfN Berlin:

- Johannes Vogel, ECSA and MfN Berlin

Appendix 2 - Online survey

Citizen Science Training Needs & Resources

This is the first survey from the EU.Citizen-Science project, which aims to create a global Citizen Science platform that features custom-made training modules that address community needs.

We need your help in compiling existing Citizen Science training resources for 'how to do citizen science' as well as general tools, guidelines and materials. In addition, we would like to know what new Citizen Science training resources are needed and which audiences should be targeted.

All survey responses are anonymous and will be used to build the platform and create new training modules. Please take a quick look at the five questions before starting. We are looking for global resources - so language doesn't matter.

Thank you for taking the time to fill out the questionnaire! :)
Muki Haklay, Christian Nold & Alice Sheppard
<http://eu-citizen.science>

Q1) Please list as many Citizen Science training resources for 'how to do citizen science' that you are aware of. (Use a separate line for each one - there is no word limit)

These could be formal courses, MOOCs, or simple handouts and videos. Please add URL's and references to the resource.

Long-answer text

Q2) Please list any high-quality Citizen Science tools, guidelines and materials. (Use a separate line for each one - there is no word limit)

For example this could be software tools, diagrams, policy reports, technical manuals for apps, etc. Please add URL's and references.

Long-answer text

Q3) In your opinion, what kinds of new training resources are needed in Citizen Science?

Please be as specific as you can in terms of training topics or skills and the format in which you would want to access this in (text, video, podcast, etc).

Long-answer text

Q4) What audience should be prioritised by these new training resources?

- Public (Citizen scientists & Newcomers to citizen science)
- Practitioners (Coordinators & Project Managers)
- Academia (Career Scientists & Researchers)
- Press (Journalists and Media Experts)
- Policymakers and civil servants
- Industry, SMEs (small-to-medium enterprises & new entrepreneurs)
- School teachers and educators
- Everybody!
- Other...

Q5) If you answered "Other" in Q4 please tell us more! Do you have any other thoughts about Citizen Science training?

Long-answer text

Appendix 3 - SwafS call text

Excerpt from the call text of the **SwafS-15-2018-2019 Exploring and supporting citizen science** call¹⁰, used for identifying potential needs for resources from the EC perspective, based on highlighted challenges and expected impacts.

“Specific Challenge:

Citizen science is blooming across all scientific disciplines and the humanities. It can potentially bring a wide variety of benefits to researchers, citizens, policy makers and society across the research and innovation cycle, e.g; it can accelerate and sometimes even make possible the production of new scientific knowledge; it can help policy makers monitor implementation and compliance with regulations; it can increase public awareness about science and feeling of ownership of policies; and it can enable faster and evidence-informed reactions to events and better territorial coverage.

At the same time there are difficulties setting up citizen science initiatives – in terms of choosing the optimum methodologies; in terms of quality assurance and validation of the outcomes; in terms of linking the various governance levels, from local to global; in terms of ensuring balanced participation of citizens (e.g. regardless of background, gender and age); in terms of integrity of methods and data; in terms of recognising the work of citizens participating in citizen science initiatives; in terms of managing large numbers of volunteers for many months or even years (and keeping them motivated and responding to their questions).

Furthermore, questions remain unanswered about the potentials of citizen science for society e.g: what is the potential number of citizen scientists and who are they? What are the costs and benefits of citizen science (e.g. in terms of scientific excellence and the economy)? What relationship can and does citizen science have to informal and formal science education? Are there limits to citizen science, and if so what are they?

For the present topic citizen science should be understood broadly, covering a range of different levels of participation, from raising public knowledge of science, encouraging citizens to participate in the scientific process by observing, gathering and processing data, right up to setting scientific agenda and co-designing and implementing science-related policies. It could also involve publication of results and teaching science.

Scope:

There are the two sub-topics:

¹⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/swafs-15-2018-2019>

A, Coordination and Support Action - CSA [Communication and Support Action] (1 project in 2018): This will provide support to citizen science at the European level. It will also create a mutual learning space where citizen science projects/participants can exchange experiences and successful strategies. It will raise awareness of citizen science among the general public, provide co-ordination support between citizen science initiatives (in particular those funded by SwafS but also working in a spirit of co-operation with established networks of citizen scientists), identify training needs with a view to developing and implementing training to help citizen scientists, and support communication between citizen science and science journalists/science media. It will also identify good practices that incentivise career scientists to engage with citizen science activities.

[...]

Expected Impact:

A. Coordination and Support Action: Strengthened networks, co-ordination and communication among citizen science projects (particularly, but not limited, to those funded by SwafS). Availability of tools, guidelines, or other materials useful to actors inexperienced in organising and supporting citizen science initiatives. Increased awareness amongst the general public of citizen science. Delivery of training to citizen scientists (or potential science practitioners) and resultant increased skills, competences, and scientific excellence. Consortia should choose a basket of indicators to measure the impact of their work against. In particular, consortia are expected to contribute to one or more of the MoRRI indicators (for instance PE1 to PE10) and to the Sustainable Development Goals[1]

[...]”

Appendix 4 - Specific resource needs

Resource needs theme	Specific needs*
Best practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Results and good practices of successful projects > Best practices for volunteer engagement and management > Best practices for how to share and visualize data results > Best practices for co-design of projects and co-design of technology > Best practices regarding different participative methods > List of examples for good practices in CS addressed to the Academia
Co-creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Co-creation guidelines for including the public to scientists > Best practices for co-design of projects and co-design of technology
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > How to publish results in science and the popular media > How to write a policy brief and communicate relevance of research to policy makers > How to present data to local politicians and creating green papers > How to create good youtube videos > How to reach decision makers > Guide on how to manage communication [...] in CS > How to understand audiences and channels to reach them (and what for) > Media dossiers, fact check guides for journalists > How to share and visualise data results for a broad audience and real world examples > How to communicate data quality, data quality requirements and data quality issues for scientific publishing (including correspondence with reviewers) > A short, simple, handbook for CS project designers with a chapter dedicated to CS project communication [...] > For scientists, how to best keep citizens interested
CS stories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Motivations of citizen scientists and academic researchers for participating/conducting citizen science projects > Interviews with CS coordinators to explain their experience > Interviews with participants to explain their feelings with participation and their needs > Champion stories of local communities > Policy impact stories
Data quality and standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Data quality standards > Guide to fit for purpose approach to data quality > How to understand data flow > Existing data gathering/quality assurance tools and data repositories > Fun video to better understand data quality assurance > Quality assurance tools and methods > How to focus on high quality data in project design > How to communicate data quality, data quality requirements and data quality issues for scientific publishing (including correspondence with reviewers) > How to encourage volunteers to submit even when they didn't find what they're looking for (importance of null data and submitting zeros)

Empowerment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Video for activists groups to do citizen science and how to combine political objectives with science > Tools to affect change with a social justice focus > Resources that allow citizen scientists to develop their own projects, to become researchers themselves, to question existing research, and develop alternatives
Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Guide on how to manage [...] engagement in CS > Written guide on recruiting and supporting participants/citizen scientists (including diversity) > Gender inclusive engagement for citizen science experiments > Best practices for volunteer engagement and management > More information on attracting people to the projects > Involvement of underrepresented audiences > Best practices regarding different participative methods > A short, simple, handbook for CS project designers with a chapter dedicated to [...] audience development. > Empirical methods and respective involvement plans > How to keep participants engaged > For scientists, how to best keep citizens interested > Podcast and/or video to give the public the whole view of citizen science projects, (with the impact of Citizen Science in every day) and how people can engage in these activities > Engagement guides > How to ensure balanced participation of citizens (e.g. regardless of background, gender and age) > How to keep volunteers motivated and responding to their questions
Evaluation of CS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Evaluation framework > How to measure intangibles, e.g. PEG, key metric vs. vanity metrics > How to measure but <i>what</i> > Evaluation and monitoring tool > More on how to measure success metrics in CS projects (qualitative and quantitative)
Event planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Event guidelines (including e.g., code of conduct) > Guidelines and material to organise physical workshops for participants
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Policy impact stories > Articles about impact of citizen science to civil society > Articles about impact of citizen science to policy making > How to make research relevant for policy > Written guide or audio toolkit on "pathways to impact" statements to include in research proposals > Tools to affect change with a social justice focus > How to reach decision makers and design projects in a way that they can have policy impact > Documentation of impacts of citizen science projects, especially societal impacts > Podcast and/or video to give the public the whole view of citizen science projects, (with the impact of Citizen Science in every day) [...] > How to bridge citizen science findings with policymakers/local government's actions

Instructables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Manual on how to start a citizen science lab > Toolkits for integrating CS with education > How to do a policy brief > How to do good youtube videos > Plug-and-play templates and software tools generated by the community to easily create (project-specific) resources > A short series of videos with how-to's for each stage of citizen science development and implementation > Practical tools: action plans, checklists etc. > A practical guide for citizens who may want to start a citizen science project > Tools, guidelines, or other materials useful to actors inexperienced in organising and supporting citizen science initiatives
Introduction to CS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Information for funders of CS on what is special and unique about CS > Media dossiers and fact check guide for journalists > How to start considering a citizen science approach for researchers to address their own research needs > Short text or short videos as brief introduction to environmental themes, explaining basic scientific facts and underlining the advantages as well as the limitations of the CS approach > Basics on the definition of citizen science > A practical guide for citizens who may want to start a citizen science project > Podcast and/or video to give the public the whole view of citizen science projects, (with the impact of Citizen Science in every day) [...] > A brief for academics to address scepticism and how to view CS as an opportunity > Text and diagrams for orientation on on existing citizen science technologies and communities > Resources that allow citizen scientists to develop their own projects
Link with formal education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Tailored written resources for school teachers, including what citizen science can do for them and how it meets their needs > Toolkits for integrating CS with education > A guide for teachers to do practical citizen science in schools
Project management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > How to coordinate (with) educators/teacher > Guide on how to manage communication and engagement in CS > Data management tools and common back office tools for citizen science initiatives > Resources for project management > Guidance on the use of reliable third party data management systems and tools > Time management to better balance contribution to different tasks > How to plan/organize/manage training for citizen scientists > Guidelines and material to organise physical workshops for participants > Resources that allow citizen scientists to develop their own projects > How to manage large numbers of volunteers for many months or even years
Project sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The funding, organisational and practical aspects of sustaining long-term projects > Text, video for researchers, policymakers and funders on how to think about the project beyond a single funding cycle > Business model planning for sustainability

Reflections on science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Something that explains what science is with examples of good and bad science > Resources that allow citizens to understand the political contexts in which research is happening and learn how to judge different kinds of research > Resources that allow citizen scientists to question existing research, and develop alternatives > Resources that make citizens understand that research is often inconclusive and hard to interpret > Resources that allow citizens to understand why science is such a wonderful and arduous task
Regulations and ethics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Code of conduct examples for event planning > Guide to EU data policy > Privacy assurance in citizen science measurements > Guidance for handling private data (including names, e-mail addresses, location, images etc.), especially under GDPR > Text on ethics and legal questions, especially regarding projects with minors > Resources on challenges in managing the ethics of citizen science and how to tackle them > How to recognise the work of citizens participating in citizen science initiatives
Research design and methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > How to make research relevant for policy > Resources to help with methodological development of citizen science questions > How to formulate a research question for participative research > How to design projects in a way that they can have policy impact > Best practice especially regarding methodology > How to define a suitable research question > Empirical methods and respective involvement plans > Resources that allow citizen scientists to become researchers themselves > How to choose the optimum methodologies
Transferability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Support for people who want to incorporate CS in European Training Network proposals and projects > How to start considering a citizen science approach for researchers to address their own research needs > Toolkits to integrate CS with education > Collective activities for CS in Humanities, Humanities within education, social sciences > How to consider a citizen science approach for researchers to address their own research needs > Video for activists groups to do citizen science and how to combine political objectives with science > Resources for citizen social science, with more of an arts/interdisciplinary focus > How to make CS transferable in other domains, e.g. how to launch CS projects in areas such as language learning and teaching, or in user engagement in creation of resources in their own language > Resources on citizen science in arts and culture > A guide for teachers to do practical citizen science in schools

**Overview of individual resource needs per theme, based on needs identified; some of them adjusted for better readability*